

A NEW PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE: GO PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE*

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Abstract: Everyone knows that hardware does not mean anything without software. Software is developed by programming languages. One of the most important factors determining the reach of software is the characteristics of the programming language. Many rich applications can be developed with a language that is fast, easy to learn, and has a large library.

The aim of this work is to provide information about the Go programming language that a powerful, fast, easy to learn programming language. Go programming language, developed by Google. Many of the deficiencies of traditional programming languages have been eliminated. It appeared in 2009 and 1.0 version was released in 2012. With the Go programming language, fast and sophisticated projects that can work on the web or in a different environment can be produced. It is an open-source programming language that is evident by the notion of rule, flexibility and speed. In a short time, he was among the fastest growing programming languages.

Keywords: *Programming Languages, Go Programming Language, Software Development, Google, Open Source Software, Web Programming*

Introduction

The Go language was originally a programming language developed by Google in 2007 by Robert Griesemer, Rob Pike and Ken Thompson. It is a static written language and has a syntax similar to that of C programming language. It provides many advanced built-in types such as garbage collection, type security, dynamic typing, variable-length arrays, and key-value maps. It also provides a rich standard library. The Go programming language was launched in November 2009 and is used in some of Google's systems.

Figure 1: Why Go Programming Language?

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Google, a large technology and company, for years C, C ++, Java, Python and so on. It uses many different programming languages. These technologies have advantages and disadvantages. You may not notice them in small or under-load projects, but they appear in large projects. These are performance, compilation (in large projects may take hours to compile the source code) security, compliance, time management, resources (hardware, money, energy, etc.) can be listed in many headings such as management (Abut and Akca; 1988; Asadi at all, 2011a; Asadi at all, 2011b; Asadi at all, 2011c) . For many years, Google has developed both an operating system for internal systems and many technologies and algorithms to solve many problems like these (Koparan at all, 2018; Of at all, 2017; Tola at all, 2017; Kocaman, 2017; Kocaman at all, 2017; Kocaman, 2016). Go programming language is one of them. The Go programming language has been initiated by Google to solve its problems. Therefore, all features added to or not added to the Go are completely determined by the software experiences of the years. If you look at the Go programming language a little bit, you might see a question like yok “Why not generics?” (Aydin at all, 2017; Kocaman and Abut, 2015; 2015; Kocaman, 2013). The answer of this question from the developer team to summarize; Generics are not fast. The point of view of Go is so clear. The goal is to create a flexible, fast and powerful language with little language capability and rule. In this article, basic features of Go programming language will be explained. The ease of bringing to the software world will be discussed. Sample codes will be explained. GoLang, which is a fast language, will be examined with its basic lines. Go programming language has many similarities to the C programming language.

Figure 2: What Programming Language Should You Learn ? (Learneroo, 2015)

1. Features Of Go Programming Language

Most important features of Go programming language are listed;

- Compile time is fast.
- Support for environment adopting patterns similar to dynamic languages. For example, type inference (b := 10 is valid declaration of a variable b of type int)
- GoLang programs are simple and safe.
- Support for Interfaces and Type embedding.
- GoLang is object oriented

To keep the GoLang simple, the following features commonly available in other similar languages are omitted in GoLang;

- Type inheritance
- Method or operator overloading
- Circular dependencies among packages
- Pointer arithmetic
- Generic programming

2. Create, Compile Go Programs

```
package main

import "fmt"

func main() {
    fmt.Println("Hello, World !\nGo is fast")
}

Hello, World !
Go is fast
```

Figure 3: First Go Program

A Go program lines length can vary from 4 lines to millions of lines. It should be written into one or more text files with the extension ".go". For example, firstapp.go. You can create a Go program use Notepad or Notepad++ in Windows, Nano in Linux, TextEdit in macOS etc. Other, you have to download Go compiler software. You can download golang.org for your operating systems.

A compiler is computer software that transforms computer code written in one programming language (the source language) into another programming language (the target language). Compilers are a type of translator that supports digital devices, primarily computers. The name compiler is primarily used for programs that translate source code from a high-level programming language to a lower level language (e.g., assembly language, object code, or machine code) to create an executable program.

Now Go Compiler stable version is 1.11. You can download Go compiler from this address: <https://golang.org/dl/>

Go compiler list (As Operating System): Windows, Linux, macOS, FreeBSD

Install Compiler on Windows;

After download Go compiler, run "setup". Compiler will be install to "Go" folder. Setup software will be make all of go environment.

You can verify installation Go compiler. Open command line (Cmd)

```
ca: Komut İstemi

Microsoft Windows [Version 10.0.17134.285]
(c) 2018 Microsoft Corporation. Tüm hakları saklıdır.

C:\Users\Mustafa>go version
go version go1.11 windows/amd64

C:\Users\Mustafa>
```

Figure 4: Check Go compiler in Windows command line

You are ready to create Go programs in Windows.

Install Compiler on Linux;

```
$ wget https://dl.google.com/go/go1.11.src.tar.gz
```

```
$ sudo tar -xvf go1.11.src.tar.gz
```

```
$ sudo mv go /usr/local
```

Prepare Go Environment;

GOROOT is the location where Go package is installed on your system.

```
$ export GOROOT=/usr/local/go
```

GOPATH is the location of your work directory. For example my project directory is ~/GoProjects

```
$ export GOPATH=$HOME/GoProjects
```

Now set the PATH variable to access go binary system wide.

```
$ export PATH=$GOPATH/bin:$GOROOT/bin:$PATH
```

You can verify installation Go compiler. Open command line (Cmd)

```
$ go version
```

```
go version go1.11 linux/amd64
```

You are ready to create Go programs in Linux.

2.1. Create First Go Program

First you have to text editor in Windows. For Example Notepad++ (You can download it <https://notepad-plus-plus.org>)

Figure 4: First Go program and result of running

Executing program;
Follow this step;

- Open any text editor and write above code
- Save this file as firstapp.go (File extension is .go)
- Open command prompt (cmd.exe in Windows)
- Go to folder where you save firstapp.go file
- Type “go run firstapp.go” in command prompt
- If there is no errors, it seem below
Hello World ! Go is Wonderful

3. Go Programming Language Rules

In a Go program, the line separator key is a line terminator. That is, individual statements don't need a special separator like “;” in C.

```

fmt.Println("Hello Students")
fmt.Println("Go is Wonderful")
    
```

Comments;

Comments are helping texts in your Go program. These lines are not compiled. In a Go program comments character are “/* */”.

```

/* These lines are comments */
    
```

Identifiers;

Go identifiers is a name used to identify a variable, function or any user defined item. It must start with a letter (A-Z) or underscore (_) . It can follow any digits (0-9)

Example;

```

section, section1, section2, _oursection
section1 = "Computer"
section2 = "Accounting"
    
```

There is not in identifier any punctuation characters. (@,\$, %)

Go programming language is a case-sensitive language. For example “School” and “school” are different.

```

School = "Kocaeli University"
school = "Istanbul University"
    
```

3.1. Variable Type Declaration

Go Types;

In a Go program you must be declare any variable or function. Basic Go types are listed below;

- Numeric
- String
- Boolean
- Derived

Numeric types;

Integer types;

uint8	Unsigned 8 bit integer (0 - 255)
uint16	Unsigned 16 bit integer (0 - 65535)
uint32	Unsigned 32 bit integer (0 - 4294967295)
uint64	Unsigned 64 bit integer (0 - 18446744073709551615)
int8	Signed 8-bit integer numbers (-128 - 127)
int16	Signed 16-bit integer numbers (-32768 - 32767)
int32	Signed 32-bit integer numbers (-2147483648 - 2147483647)
int64	Signed 8-bit integer numbers (-9223372036854775808 - 9223372036854775807)

Floating types;

float32	32 bit real numbers
float64	64 bit real numbers
complex64	Complex number with float32
complex128	Complex number with float64

byte (like uint8), rune (like int32), uint (32/64 bits), int (like uint), uintptr (Unsigned integer of a pointer value) types are other numeric types.

Variable declaring;

If you use any variable you must declare it.

var variable_name variable_type;

Example;

var a, b, c, d int

var amount, total float32

var day = 20 /* Variable can be initialized in declaration */

This using is without type declaration. The type is determined according to the value.

a := 50 /* a type is int*/

```

1 package main
2
3 import "fmt"
4
5 func main() {
6     var a float64
7     a = 100
8     b := 200
9     name := "Mustafa"
10    fmt.Println("a value =", a)
11    fmt.Printf("Type of a variable is %T\n", a)
12    fmt.Println("b value =", b)
13    fmt.Printf("Type of b variable is %T\n", b)
14    fmt.Println("name value =", name)
15    fmt.Printf("Type of name variable is %T\n", name)
16
17 }
    
```

```

C:\GoProjects>go run vartype.go
a value = 100
Type of a variable is float64
b value = 200
Type of b variable is int
name value = Mustafa
Type of name variable is string
C:\GoProjects>
    
```

Figure 5: Variable declaring

Declaring constant;

const variable type = value

const height int = 100

const pinumber float32 = 3.14

```

1 package main
2
3 import "fmt"
4
5 func main() {
6     var radius float32
7     var area float32
8     radius = 10
9     const pinumber float32 = 3.14
10    area = radius * pinumber * pinumber
11    fmt.Println("Radius =", radius)
12    fmt.Println("Area =", area, " m2")
13 }
    
```

```

C:\GoProjects>go run circlearea.go
Radius = 10
Area = 98.59601 m2
C:\GoProjects>
    
```

Figure 6: Variable and constants declaring

3.2. Operators

We make various operations when working with variables. Arithmetic or logical operations. Operator symbol is a decision of this operation. In a Go program you will find operators are listed;

- Arithmetic
- Relational
- Logical
- Bitwise
- Assignment

Arithmetic operators;

+	Sum	c = a + b
-	Subtracts	c = a - b
*	Multiply	c = a * b
/	Divide	c = a / b
%	Modulus	c = a % b
++	Increment	c++
--	Decrement	c--

```

1 package main
2
3 import "fmt"
4
5 func main() {
6     var a float32 = 100
7     var b float32 = 10
8     var c float32
9     c = a + b;
10    fmt.Println("Sum :", c)
11    c = a - b;
12    fmt.Println("Subtract :", c)
13    c = a * b;
14    fmt.Println("Multiply :", c)
15    c = a / b;
16    fmt.Println("Divide :", c)
17    var c1 int
18    c1 = 10 % 3;
19    fmt.Println("Modulus :", c1)
20    var d int = 5
21    d++
22    fmt.Println("Increment :", d)
23    d--
24    fmt.Println("Decrement :", d)
25 }
    
```

```

C:\GoProjects>go run arithmeticop.go
Sum : 110
Subtract : 90
Multiply : 1000
Divide : 10
Modulus : 1
Increment : 6
Decrement : 5
C:\GoProjects>
    
```

Figure 7: Arithmetic operations

Assignment operators;

These operators are Go programming language assignment operators. These are listed below.

Operator	Description	Example
=	Assign values right to the left	$c = d + f$
+=	Sum and assign	$c += d \rightarrow c = c + d$
-=	Subtract and assign	$c -= d \rightarrow c = c - d$
*=	Multiply and assign	$c *= d \rightarrow c = c * d$
/=	Divide and assign	$c /= d \rightarrow c = c / d$
%=	Modulus and assign	$c \% = d \rightarrow c = c \% d$
<<=	Left shift and assign	$c << = d \rightarrow c = c << d$
>>=	Right shift and assign	$c >> = d \rightarrow c = c >> d$
&=	Bitwise And then assign	$c \& = d \rightarrow c = c \& d$
=	Bitwise Or then assign	$c = d \rightarrow c = c d$
^=	Bitwise exclusive Or then assign	$c \wedge = d \rightarrow c = c \wedge d$

Relational operators;

These operators are using to compare variables. Suppose $c = 5, d = 6$

Operator	Description	Example
==	Checks two operands equality	$c == d \rightarrow$ not true
!=	Checks two operands equality	$c != d \rightarrow$ true
>	Checks two operands great than	$c > d \rightarrow$ not true
<	Checks two operands less than	$c < d \rightarrow$ true
>=	Checks two operands great or equal than	$c >= d \rightarrow$ not true
<=	Checks two operands less or equal than	$c <= d \rightarrow$ true

Figure 8: Relational operations

Logical operators;

Go programming language logical operators are listed. Suppose $c = 1, b = 0$

Operator	Description	Example
&&	If both operands are true (as logical) then result is true (AND)	$c \&\& d \rightarrow$ false
&&	If any operands are true (as logical) then result is true (OR)	$c d \rightarrow$ true
!	Reverse logical condition. (NOT)	$!(c d) \rightarrow$ false

```

1 package main
2
3 import "fmt"
4
5 func main() {
6     var c bool = true
7     var d bool = false
8     if( c && d){
9         fmt.Println("Condition 1 (AND): Logical condition is true")
10    }
11    if( c || d){
12        fmt.Println("Condition 2 (OR): Logical condition is true")
13    }
14    if( ! (c && d)){
15        fmt.Println("Condition 3 (NOT): Logical condition is true")
16    }
17 }

```

```

C:\GoProjects>go run logicalop.go
Condition 2 (OR): Logical condition is true
Condition 3 (NOT): Logical condition is true
C:\GoProjects>

```

Figure 9: Logical operations

Bitwise operators;

These operators work on bits and run bit by bit operation.

& (AND) , | (OR), ^ (Exclusive OR), ~ (NOT)

<< (Left shift), >> (Right Shift)

Suppose c = 5 and d = 6

c is 5 (decimal), 00000101 (binary)

d is 6 (decimal), 00000110 (binary)

c = 00000101

d = 00000110

&-----

Result is 00000100 (binary) and 4 (decimal)

c = 00000101

d = 00000110

|-----

Result is 00000111 (binary) and 7 (decimal)

c = 00000101

d = 00000110

^----- (Same "|" operator. Different is only "true ^ true" is false)

Result is 00000011 (binary) and 3 (decimal)

~c 00000101

Result is 11111010 (binary), 372 (decimal)

Conclusions

The Go programming language is quite simple and comfortable. It is completely open source. It has a fast compilation structure. Provides increased speed of operation with large data. The standard library is wide. Go programming language is a good choice for programmers who are looking for a new programming language. This article describes the basic characteristics of Go programming language. This language will provide a basis for new programmers.

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